

Bhairavapadmāvatīkalpa

By Aaron Michael Ullrey, University of Houston, University of Naropa

Entry tags: Digambara, Religious Group, Text, Magic, Scripture, Ritual text, Jain Traditions, Tantra

A 10c. Jain tantra text (kalpa) on the topic of magic, sorcery, divination, medicine, snake-bite cures, and varied transactions with yakṣa beings. It is composed by Mallisena and accompanied by a detailed gloss by Bandhusena. The text is published as an appendix in Jhahvery's *Critical Study of Mantrasastra*. The text is one of a few Jain tantras that advocate violent rituals. The text suggests that these tenth century Jains of Mysore were actively engaged in the pan-South Asian ritual culture of magic. This text is NOT a Jain endorsement of aggressive magic, but it does demonstrate that some Jains at some times thought and wrote about these magic rituals.

Date Range: 900 CE - 1100 CE

Region: Mysore

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

The Mysore Kingdom according to the 1799 Treaty of Seringapatam.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jhahvery Mohanlal Bhagwandas and Malliṣeṇasūri Malliṣeṇasūri. *Comparative and Critical Study of Mantrasastra with Special Treatment of Jain Mantravada Being the Introduction to Sri Bhairava Padmavati Kalpa*. Sarabhai Manilal Nawab 1944.
- Source 2: Malliṣeṇasūri Malliṣeṇasūri and Caturvedī Śukadeva. *Bhairavapadmāvatīkalpa : Saṃskṛta Vivaraṇa Evaṃ "mohinī" Hindī Vyākhyā Sahita*. 1. saṃskaraṇa ed. Motīlāla Banārasīdāsa Pabliśarsa 1999.
- Source 3: Malliṣeṇasūri Malliṣeṇasūri et al. *Śrī Bhairavapadmāvatīkalpa*. 2. samvṛddhita āvṛtti ed. Sārābhāī Maṇilāla Navāba 1996.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://erenow.net/common/goddess-traditions-in-tantric-hinduism/4.php>
- Source 1 Description: <https://alexandria.ucsb.edu/downloads/3t945r069>
- Source 2 URL: https://www.academia.edu/42205862/Jain_Tantric_Literature?auto=download

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://alexandria.ucsb.edu/downloads/3t945r069>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Published in print several versions in the twentieth and twenty first century. Handwritten manuscripts are located at the Bhandarkar Research Institute and also at the Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Government Oriental Library Mysore. It appears to also be found in manuscripts at Arrah, but I have not consulted physically.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: MSS found on the standard wood pulp paper dating from the modern era. Palm leaf manuscripts are much older.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: Some manuscripts have marginalia notes.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– I don't know

Notes: Likely stored in the past in sanskrit archives associated with Jain temples.

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Published in print several versions in the twentieth and twenty first century. Handwritten manuscripts are located at the Bhandarkar Research Institute and also at the Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Government Oriental Library Mysore. It appears to also be found in manuscripts at Arrah, but I have not consulted physically. Versions are still being published today.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: It is associated with Jainism, but its contexts are necessarily heterodox, but they may not have been heterodox at the time. It appears there was a robust discourse about magic in the kingdom of Mysore during the 10th century.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

Notes: Another Jain tantra describes an origination from the mouth of a possessed devotee. This text only talks about the importance of the text and its association with the Tirthankara named Parsvanatha.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: Commentaries and interpretations and glosses are added in varied version that are manuscripts or printed texts.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– I don't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Groups like lay clerics such as Bhattarakas in the South or Yatis in the north may have been experts and deployed such ritual sources.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Groups like lay clerics such as Bhattarakas in the South or Yatis in the north may have been experts and deployed such ritual sources.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Sanskrit is archaic but it is also the lingua franca among medieval folk

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: Text is found with sanskrit gloss in lower register. There is writing on and commentary and gloss in modern versions in modern vernaculars.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Notes: It has some distinct styles of writing for magical diagrams with rendered mantras.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: Sanskrit is the language of the gods!

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– I don't know

Notes: I would guess the Mysore kings were involved in supporting this type of lore and were definitely involved in patronizing sanskrit learning.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– I don't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: Not according to the text, but Jains generally seek converts.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text is declared to be essential, to be very important. And its learning is declared to be paramount, and this suggests a certain level of proselytizing,

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Jains generally are required to share their message which is the only way to reduce harm and the negative karmas inherent in life.

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: No details on spreading the word, but the word is to be spread.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: This is a digambara text, so it is a reform out of primal Jainism, but since it is tantra it is clearly a reform of Jain orthodoxy and practices.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Mantras are recited, though they are often in code. Magical diagrams set out. Divination. Medicine using ritual and mantra, especially for snakebite. Rituals to enable seduction and sexual subjugation.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 5

Notes: Most of the rituals are only done by an individual or by a sorcerer for a client, but some divinations rituals, in particular, have multiple participants.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Often or rarely. They are not regularly performed. They are votive.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Notes: A teacher might check to see if the rituals are done right, but it seems the rituals effectiveness is its own proof of proper performance.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Notes: A teacher might check to see if the rituals are done right, but it seems the rituals effectiveness is its own proof of proper performance.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: I would argue the text is inherently synchronic by absorbing Hindu magic practices. The deities in questions are not clearly originating in either Hinduism or Jainism or Buddhism, since they are Yakshas.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The intoxicants are mostly ritual ingredients, but the goal is not the intoxication of performers.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Pleasant and noxious foods are consumed, not like sacrament but as ritual actions and ingredients.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: A book of magic rituals, not a book that is magic.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: there are special calligraphy for inscribing mantras in magic diagrams

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: Printed versions of the text have images of the deities and magic diagrams. Manuscript versions sometimes have simple line drawings.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are many manuscripts and there are also many printed versions. Some are more complete than others. I would argue the more complete the text or the longer the text the more it is considered authoritative.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: It is called a kalpa but it is a tantra. It is contiguous with the world of magic in the medieval tantras.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: There are some index verses at the opening that list the contents.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is a lineage of gurus that transmit the text and also a chain of supernatural entities that reveal the text.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Esoteric ritual

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: It arguably appeals to normative Jainism, but then it expresses many rituals that are contrary to Jainism.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Specific rituals are done at specific times of the year, day, month, but there is not a ritual calendar that organizes all the rites.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: the Jain spirit or soul is grossly connected to the body and karmas, but it is itself free and luminous.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Independent but hindered by body.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: Anything that is connected to the world and perception is considered hindering to the soul.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Unique jain epistemological ontology.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: I mean.....they do not really debate. The should and the world and the bindings of karma is constant and accepted, but the nature of these facts are debated.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: Karmas accrued through all action in life are framed as the cause of bondage and the cause of not realizing the should.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The soul or individual Jiva is stuck in the body due to karma

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: This is a digambara text, which is a minority group to the Svetambaras, and within the text this one is a ritual magic text which would be necessarily even more minor.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

Notes: Afterlife is immediate reincarnation as human, with the possibility of divine or demonic rebirth in heaven or hells, though these are only temporary states.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Notes: The universe is described in the form of a man, and above the main are the siddhai, perfected beings who exist, unmoving in a place characterized by light and tremendous wind. But humans in these eras now will only be reborn in the worlds below these perfected beings.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: All afterlife experiences are temporary

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: This text does not engage these Jain notions but would have maintained mainstream ideas, despite their heterodox practices.

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

Notes: theoretically you can be reborn as an animal or plant. Animal incarnations are common in narratives about sin leading to poor rebirth.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

Notes: Karma is a physical thing that dictates rebirth.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

Notes: There is a vague possibility of meritorious beings to be reborn as attendants to future Jinas.

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

–Specify: Reincarnation for all.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Hard to say.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– I don't know

Notes: This question does not work. The world is not created. But there are many gods with whom humans interact.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: Perfected spirits can become perfected beings called siddhai, but this only happened in prior eras. Those perfected beings do not act and thinking would be considered an action. They are completely unaffected by the world.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: They do not act, so they cannot effect anything.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Notes: If there were a spirit between lives they would be propelled by memory.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: In principle there are all sorts of deities and spirits that can appear.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: A wide range of entities who are non human can show up. Some are more powerful than others. None are perfected or enlightened. The range of knowledge and power depends on the specific entity.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: They especially know the future rebirths of a person due to karmas and actions.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: They have all sorts of effects, depending on the being and its intention.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that some rakshas and past jins appear and reveal the contents of scriptures.

↳ In dreams?

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: Some evidence in divination here.

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: Divination practices seem to be sometimes linked to entities communicating

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: I think when they have effect it is direct.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: When in a good mood or pious they are good to people.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: When angered or not pious they are negative and hostile.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: Karma is inescapable and mechanical. The jinas are beyond all action.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Specific beings may do negative things, but karma is mechanical and not escapable.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: beings invoked and placated can bestow reward

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes benefit only requires the ritual to be done properly.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Notes: The text writes about the importance of being good and selfless, but the rituals within are entirely selfish.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The reincarnation is pretty immediate, unless someone attains a rebirth in a god realm, which is very rare.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Most of these rewards are in fact the results of specific magic rituals that bring about reproductive success, victory in battle (supported by a divine yaksha warrior aiding them in battle), wealth, success in the court, perpetual health, and healing practices, especially from poison and snakebite.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The many Jinas in the past are sorta like prophets, but they have individual attainment that affects no others except that they can spread teachings.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: There are endless cycles of ages, and we are toward the end of one era. This cycle will end and then it will all start again. Infinitely in the future and infinitely in the past.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Jainism has social norms, and the text frames itself so that practitioners should maintain these ideals, but the vast majority of the text contents are violent and thereby against Jainism.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: It seems like there would be, but there is no real distinction, despite putting forth ideals at one moment and rituals that contradict them at another.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: From the opening chapter: The mantrin's pride and amour are conquered, wrath tranquilized, irrelevant speech abandoned. He delights worshipping the goddess [Padmāvātī] and reveres the feet of the the Jina. (6) The mantrin is such a man who is heroic (śūra) in mantra performance, eschews sins (pāpa), resolute in virtue, solemn (maunī), and he is pious in spirit (mahābhīmānī). (7) He was initiated by a venerable guru (gurūjanahitopadeśa), is not slothful, rejects [excessive], and eats only measured amounts of food. He worships the goddess [Padmāvātī]. (8) He has conquered his senses and defects [i.e. the products of the five senses and defects such as anger]. His [only] bodily-delight is engendered by the nectar of Dharma. He is endowed with the most weighty of virtues. (9) In the midst of the world, the mantrin is pure [inside and out], placid, devoted to Gurudevas, maintains vows (vrata), truthful,

compassionate, intelligent, shrewd, and well-lettered (bījapadāvadhārin) [i.e. able to discern and divide words and seed-syllables.]. (10) Wherever and whenever [i.e. despite the situation, temporal or locative], if these qualities are not present in a man, he will not be a mantrin. If he practices mantra recitation due to haughtiness (darpavaśa), he will only attain false-hood (anartha) [even in the presence] of Padāvatī.(11)

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: This is tricky because Jainism abhors violence but glorifies violent actions.

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Physical potency is important for any spiritual development
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope
– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– I don't know

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– I don't know

Notes: Ideally the practitioner should be celibate, since this is jainism, but there are rituals for sexual subjugation and reproduction.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Notes: Male monogamy is not an ideal in India at the time, but the ideal Jain male is celibate. Th at said, this text is filled with sexual rituals.

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Notes: Ideally all Jains, especially women are celibate. But the practitioners are given rituals for sex.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Fasting is required for certain rituals, and Jains aspire to a fasting death, but the text has no overarching argument or prescription about fasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: All dependent on the specific rituals.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Valuable items are required to perform the rituals.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals are long, others are short.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Notes: All these rituals require danger and risk to perform and to interact with dangerous substances and entities.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The opening chapter and closing chapter require a practitioner to be a good Jain, but then the rituals are very non-Jain

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Magic rituals are by their nature private and occasional, based on the specific need or end desired.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Notes: All the rituals are occasional

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: the practitioner must perform the offerings required of the rituals

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– I don't know

Notes: General worship is accompanied by good smells like incense. Magic rites may also have noxious smells.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes the actions and offerings are by making magic diagrams which have all sorts of prescriptions on colors.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: There are no regular worship spaces for the rituals. That said, each ritual will require the preparation of a space to be maintained in the course of the ritual.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A tribe

Notes: Elite and educated Jains can command a similar status as Brahmins, though they are outside the Hindu caste system

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: No institutional per se but individual Jains are called to attend to welfare of the world and the people who are suffering. Special care to suffering animals.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– I don't know

Notes: No institutional per se but individual Jains are called to attend to welfare of the world and the people who are suffering. Special care to suffering animals.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: It seems that a practitioner should learn from a guru teacher.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Authority and clerical status is diffuse among Jains, though a renunciate will always be considered higher than a layperson.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Reverence to gurus. Also to the varied authorities of Jainism.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Using the text will gain incredible power and luck.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Despite Jainism being against violence, the ideals of the warrior are found throughout the text. Also there is a great amount of warfare magic. It does not explicitly glorify winning or bemoan loss, but it enables rites to cause victory.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– I don't know

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– I don't know

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No